

Percent of leaves damaged by LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* on different rice varieties in valleys of the hilly regions of UP, India, 1991 kharif.

Valley	Variety	Av leaf damage (%)
Gagas Valley (1,100 m asl) ^a	Govind	85
	Pant Dhan 6	72
	VL-16	80
	Local	55
Garur Valley (1,200 m asl)	Govind	86
	VL-16	85
	VLK39	78
	Local	62
Someswar Valley (1,350 m ad)	Govind	77
	Pant Dhan 6	65
	VL-8	72
	Local	45
Bageswar Valley (1,000 m asl)	Govind	65
	IR24	72
	Saket 4	60
	Local	48
Chaukhtutia Valley (1,000 m asl)	Govind	78
	IR24	70
	Saket 4	82
	Local	54

^am asl = meters above sea level.

were reared in the laboratory for identification.

The insects appeared in July and remained until October. Infestation peaked from early Aug through late Sep. Average leaf damage was 45-86%. High-yielding dwarf varieties suffered more damage than local tall varieties (see table). Such a high LF incidence in the region's irrigated transplanted rice had not been recorded for 15-20 yr.

The Department of Plant Protection and Agriculture organized a campaign to control LF in infested areas. Chlorpyrifos 20 EC and monocrotophos 40 EC sprayed at 0.5 liter ai/ha gave effective control. □

Assessing the prevalence of rice pests in Cambodia

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Current information on the prevalence of insects and diseases in Cambodia is scanty. In 1990, the Cambodia-IRRI Rice Project sponsored in Phnom Penh a training course on problem diagnosis in rice. After the course, the 90 participants collected insect and disease baseline data in 261 fields in 12 provinces.

Using a zigzag sampling pattern, they examined 15 hills/field. For each hill,

they assessed disease severity (%) and insect injury (%) and estimated insect number by sweepnet. Prevalence was calculated as the proportion of fields in which specific diseases, insects, or beneficial arthropods were found, expressed as a percentage of the total number of fields visited. All fields were visited once from tillering to milk grain stage, and 102 fields were visited a second time from booting to ripening. The stage at which observations were made could not be standardized because of asynchronous planting and the difficulty of visiting fields.

Nearly 80% of the fields sampled were planted to traditional rice varieties, the most common being Phka Khney (8.0% of fields). IR36 and IR42 were the dominant modern varieties, respectively occupying 10.3 and 7.6% of the surveyed fields.

Brown spot (BS) was the most prevalent disease followed by narrow brown spot (Table 1). BS incidence, based on the number of infected tillers, was high in all provinces and in all varieties throughout the crop growth stages. BS was severe in variety Chhmar Prom during the first observation. The widespread occurrence and high incidence of BS may be due to poor plant nutrition, which is a

predisposing factor for the disease.

In most provinces, green leafhoppers (GLH) and brown planthoppers (BPH) were most prevalent during the first observation, followed by spiders and beetles (Table 2). In Takeo and Kompong Speu Provinces, there were more GLH on Phka Khney and IR50 varieties and at tillering to booting stages; more BPH were seen in Svay Rieng Province and on traditional varieties. Spiders and beetles were present throughout crop growth, but in low numbers.

Damage caused by hispa, cutworms, rice gall midge (GM), rice leaffolder, and stemborers was common in most provinces (Table 2). GM damage generally declined from tillering to milk grain stage in contrast to that of hispa, which gradually increased from tillering to flowering in the first observation. Percent insect damage generally increased with growth stage in the second observation, but in general, the insect population and damage were lower in the second observation than in the first observation.

We reported only pest prevalence and not incidence or severity of pest attack because we could not calibrate the

Table 1. Prevalence of rice diseases in provinces of Cambodia, 1990 wet season.

Province	Fields (no.)	Prevalence (% of fields)						
		Brown spot	Narrow brown spot	Bacterial blight	Bacterial leaf streak	Leaf blight	Leaf scald	Sheath blight
<i>First observation</i>								
Banteay Meanchey	10	50.0	20.0	30.0	20.0	60.0	0.0	10.0
Battambang	15	80.0	13.3	6.1	0.0	33.3	0.0	0.0
Kandal	76	34.2	1.3	10.5	10.5	1.3	2.6	0.0
Kompong Cham	10	100.0	20.0	40.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Chhnang	9	88.9	22.2	0.0	11.1	11.1	0.0	0.0
Kompong Speu	16	100.0	6.2	0.0	6.2	6.2	0.0	0.0
Kompong Thorn	10	30.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Phnom Penh	41	92.7	24.4	2.4	12.2	9.8	0.0	9.8
Prey Veng	11	63.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Pursat	3	66.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Svay Rieng	15	33.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Takeo	45	84.4	20.0	6.7	2.2	11.1	0.0	0.0
<i>Second observation</i>								
Battambang	9	88.9	55.5	11.1	0.0	22.2	0.0	0.0
Kandal	15	11.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Cham	5	100.0	20.0	80.0	40.0	40.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Chhnang	2	0.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Kompong Speu	13	38.5	30.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Phnom Penh	10	90.0	50.0	0.0	30.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Prey Veng	5	100.0	60.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Svay Rieng	6	83.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Takeo	20	100.0	0.0	20.0	0.0	30.0	0.0	0.0

Table 2. Prevalence based on counts of insect pests and natural enemies and on damage on rice in provinces of Cambodia, 1990 wet season.

Province	Prevalence (% of fields)														
	Fields (no.)	Count							Damage						
		Insect pests			Natural enemies				Hispa	Case-worm	Leaf-folder	Cut-worm	Whorl maggot	Gall midge	Stem-borer
	Green leaf-hopper	Brown plant-hopper	Rice bug	Spiders	Beetles	Micraspis	Cyrthorhinus								
<i>First observation</i>															
Banteay Meanchey	9	100.0	88.9	0.0	100.0	33.3	0.0	0.0	22.2	11.1	33.3	77.8	22.2	88.9	55.6
Battambang	10	100.0	100.0	0.0	50.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	20.0	50.0	100.0	100.0	40.0	10.0
Kandal	68	92.6	75.0	0.0	32.4	13.2	0.0	0.0	64.7	77.9	66.2	73.5	50.0	58.8	72.1
Kompong Cham	10	40.0	10.0	0.0	40.0	10.0	20.0	10.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	10.0
Kompong Chhnang	9	55.6	33.3	0.0	33.3	11.1	0.0	11.1	33.3	22.2	44.4	55.6	0.0	11.1	55.6
Kompong Speu	16	87.5	50.0	0.0	62.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.0	12.5	0.0	50.0	43.7	56.2	25.0
Kompong Thom	6	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	83.3	83.3	100.0	83.3	100.0	83.3
Phnom Penh	35	100.0	91.4	0.0	65.7	31.4	2.9	0.0	77.1	57.1	77.1	80.0	54.3	94.3	71.4
Prey Veng	11	90.9	90.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	27.3	9.1	27.3	9.1	0.0	90.9	72.7
Pursat	4	100.0	75.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	25.0
Svay Rieng	10	50.0	50.0	30.0	50.0	0.0	50.0	0.0	50.0	50.0	40.0	50.0	40.0	50.0	50.0
Takeo	45	91.1	77.8	0.0	42.2	22.2	0.0	0.0	68.9	66.7	62.2	44.4	40.0	66.7	51.1
<i>Second observation</i>															
Banteay Meanchey	10	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	20.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	90.0	50.0	70.0	60.0	40.0
Battambang	10	70.0	0.0	0.0	30.0	10.0	0.0	0.0	60.0	30.0	80.0	100.0	80.0	30.0	30.0
Kandal	21	61.9	4.8	0.0	42.9	66.7	0.0	33.3	47.6	61.9	38.1	66.7	47.6	47.6	76.2
Kompong Cham	5	0.0	0.0	0.0	80.0	40.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	80.0
Kompong Chhnang	1	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Kompong Speu	14	71.4	7.1	0.0	57.1	28.6	0.0	0.0	35.7	0.0	57.1	35.8	14.3	7.1	35.7
Phnom Penh	13	30.8	23.1	0.0	15.4	7.7	0.0	7.7	76.9	46.2	30.8	0.0	46.2	23.1	61.5
Prey Veng	2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Svay Rieng	6	100.0	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0	0.0	83.3	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	66.7	83.3	100.0
Takeo	20	75.0	5.0	45.0	95.0	80.0	0.0	50.0	100.0	50.0	90.0	85.0	55.0	55.0	90.0

precision of the many observers working under difficult conditions. We were confident only about the accuracy of pest identification and the presence or absence of a pest in a field.

The survey results show that the insects and diseases common to other rice ecosystems are present in Cambodia where traditional varieties are widely grown and farm inputs are at a marginal

level. Pest dynamics should be monitored under the current farm situation in anticipation of increases in the area grown to modern varieties and in input use. □

Early spraying by rice farmers in Leyte, Philippines.

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We found that 88.7% of 300 farmers surveyed in Leyte applied pesticides—mostly insecticides during the 1991 wet season (WS). The majority of these farmers sprayed early, with 77% spraying within 30 d of transplanting. Of the total sprays throughout the

survey season, almost half were applied at the vegetative phase, with the largest percentage (37%) at tillering. Farmers usually sprayed two-three times, although some sprayed up to seven times (Fig. 1).

The target pests of these early sprays were mostly leaf-feeders, which farmers perceived to be the main pest problems at tillering. The leaf-feeders that farmers cited included rice leafhoppers, cutworms, armyworms, whorl maggots, grasshoppers, and ladybird beetles. The most common insecticides used for their control were endosulfan, monocrotophos, methyl parathion, cypermethrin, and chlorpyrifos.

Studies have shown that leaf-feeding insects that damage rice plants at the early crop stages do not cause sufficient yield loss to justify spraying. This implies that most of the early sprays made by farmers are unnecessary.

Farmers sprayed early because they perceived leaf-feeding insects to cause severe yield loss. Many (86%) also believed that the chemicals they used were effective in controlling or preventing these pests. This may have accounted for the farmers' use of toxic insecticides at the early crop stages.

The majority of the farmers (81%) thought that insecticide applications